

IMPROVING PD-L1 EXPRESSION PREDICTION IN NON-SMALL CELL LUNG CANCER USING RADIOMIC ANALYSIS AND ENSEMBLE MACHINE LEARNING MODELS ON WHOLE-BODY VS. LUNG PET/CT DATA

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Abstract Lung cancer remains the leading cause of cancer-related mortality globally. Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) account for 85% of lung cancer cases. Programmed Death-Ligand 1 (PD-L1) is a critical biomarker in NSCLC for guiding immunotherapy, yet conventional detection methods, such as immunohistochemistry, are invasive and insufficiently capture tumour heterogeneity. This study explores the potential of radiomics-based machine learning (ML) models to predict PD-L1 expression using whole-body and lung [¹⁸F]-FDG PET/CT imaging data. Radiomic features were extracted from 134,590 whole-body and 43,142 lung slices obtained from 308 NSCLC patients. The study evaluated the performance of ensemble models including random forest, and XGBoost at feature- and patient-level analyses. Models trained on whole-body data consistently outperformed those using lung data, highlighting the importance of systemic metabolic information. At the feature level, the random forest model achieved 99.1% accuracy and an ROC-AUC of 0.998. Similarly, at the patient-level, the random forest model also achieved 98% accuracy and an ROC-AUC of 0.995. The findings demonstrate the superiority of whole-body radiomic analysis over localised imaging for predicting PD-L1 expression. This approach underscores its potential as a non-invasive diagnostic tool, providing an advanced framework for precision oncology in NSCLC management.

1. INTRODUCTION

Lung cancer remains the leading cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide, with 1.8 million people dying of lung cancer every year [1], highlighting the urgent need for more effective diagnostic and therapeutic strategies. In the United Kingdom, lung cancer is the third most prevalent cancer [2]. About 85% of lung cancer is classified as non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC). Over the past decade, the treatment landscape for NSCLC has evolved significantly and in addition to traditional modalities such as surgery, radiotherapy and chemotherapy, more targeted therapies and immunotherapies determined by tumour expression of molecular markers have been added to the treatment armamentarium [3]. Personalized biomarker-driven NSCLC therapy targeting epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR), anaplastic lymphoma kinase (ALK), and immunotherapy targeting the programmed death-ligand 1 (PD-L1) is now available [4].

Immunotherapy, particularly through the use of immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs) targeting the PD-1/PD-L1 pathway, have emerged as a key treatment modality of NSCLC management. By blocking the interaction between PD-L1 on tumour cells and PD-1 on T-cells, these agents reactivate the immune response, leading to significant improvements in progression-free and overall survival compared to traditional chemotherapy [5][6][7][8][9][10]. However, the standard method for assessing PD-L1 expression—immunohistochemistry (IHC)—requires invasive biopsies that may not capture tumour heterogeneity and can lead to complications [11][12][13]. This limitation underscores the need for non-invasive, comprehensive assessment methods.

To address these limitations, there is a growing interest in leveraging the radiomic features of computerised tomography (CT) and positron emission tomography/CT (PET/CT) with [¹⁸F]fluorodeoxyglucose ([¹⁸F]FDG) beyond its traditional diagnostic and monitoring roles, particularly in quantitative biomarker evaluation for immunotherapy response prediction [14]. Alongside conventional radiotracer uptake evaluation performed using Standardized Uptake Value (SUV), a widely used PET imaging metric for assessing tumor metabolism, advanced computational approaches such as artificial intelligence and machine learning enhance the extraction and interpretation of high dimensional features from PET/CT scans. By analyzing the shape, intensity, and texture features of tumors, radiomics provides a noninvasive method to assess tumor biology and predict therapeutic outcomes [15][16][17].

Early radiomics models for PD-L1 prediction, despite demonstrating moderate performance (with accuracies around 68% and AUCs ranging from 0.706 to 0.84 [18][19]), face a critical research gap. These models are predominantly based on small datasets, leading to overfitting and compromised generalizability which is a serious concern for clinical applications. Moreover, their focus on localized tumour regions neglects systemic metabolic activity, an important facet of tumour biology that could significantly enhance predictive accuracy. This oversight reveals a clear problem in current methodologies: the inability to fully capture the complex, systemic nature of tumour behaviour. Addressing this gap by incorporating systemic metabolic information into radiomic analyses is essential for developing more robust and clinically applicable models for PD-L1 prediction.

To overcome these challenges, ensemble machine learning models, particularly random forest and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), have demonstrated strong performance in medical imaging analysis and disease classification by reducing overfitting and improving model interpretability. random forest has demonstrated significant success in disease risk classification, including maternal health risk prediction, where an ensemble model combining random forest and artificial neural networks (ANN) achieved high accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score in classifying pregnancy-related complications [20]. Similarly, a study analysing highly imbalanced disease datasets found that random forest, coupled with repeated random sub-sampling, outperformed other classifiers in predicting the risk of eight chronic diseases, achieving superior sensitivity and specificity compared to traditional methods [21]. In clinical disease prediction, random forest models have effectively classified conditions such as diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and cancer, with a reported accuracy exceeding 90% in multiple datasets [22]. Likewise, XGBoost has been widely applied in cancer diagnostics, where it achieved an accuracy of 94.74% and a recall of 95.24% in breast cancer classification, underscoring its efficacy in early disease detection [23]. Additionally, XGBoost has been successfully utilized for classifying 28 different cancer types based on circulating tumour DNA, demonstrating its ability to handle complex, high-dimensional genetic data [24].

In NSCLC research, ensemble models have shown promise in non-invasive tumour characterization. A study comparing random forest models trained on CT radiomics versus semantic features found that models incorporating semantic descriptors interpreted by radiologists achieved higher accuracy in classifying NSCLC subtypes than radiomics-based models alone [25]. Further advancements in tumour microenvironment analysis have leveraged an expert-in-the-loop random forest model to distinguish adenocarcinoma from squamous cell carcinoma in fibrotic and non-fibrotic lung regions, highlighting the model's ability to capture subtle variations in tissue morphology [26]. Moreover, the integration of random forest and XGBoost in lung cancer prediction has significantly enhanced classification performance, with hyperparameter tuning and ensemble voting mechanisms improving predictive accuracy beyond standalone models [27]. These studies collectively underscore the potential of ensemble methods in improving cancer classification and prognosis.

Building on these advances, this study employs random forest and XGBoost to predict PD-L1 expression in NSCLC patients using radiomic features extracted from [^{18}F]FDG PET/CT scans. By integrating both whole-body and lung imaging data at the feature and patient levels, our approach aims to capture broader systemic metabolic activity and overcome the constraints of localized analysis. Ultimately, this strategy is expected to enhance the accuracy, robustness, and clinical applicability of PD-L1 expression prediction, providing a non-invasive and scalable framework to guide immunotherapy decisions in NSCLC patients.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Data Collection

The present research utilized imaging and tissue expression data collated for an institutionally-approved audit from 308 patients diagnosed with non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) who

underwent ^{18}F -fluorodeoxyglucose (^{18}F FDG) positron emission tomography/computed tomography (PET/CT) examinations at the Nuclear Medicine Department of Castle Hill Hospital between December 2019 and January 2023. Among these patients, 207 were classified as PD-L1-positive and 101 as PD-L1-negative based on immunohistochemistry (IHC) analyses. Imaging data were stored in Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) format and retrieved using Mirada DBx software. The scans consisted of fused PET/CT images with attenuation correction applied to enhance image quality and ensure quantitative accuracy. Each patient's PET/CT scan produced more than 300 axial slices representing cross-sectional images of the body. For targeted analysis, slices numbered 120 to 260, representing the thoracic region encompassing the lungs, were selected based on consultations with a radiologist and validation using the Mirada DBx viewer. To protect patient privacy, all data were anonymized in accordance with ethical guidelines. The dataset exhibited class imbalance, with 67% of cases classified as PD-L1-positive and 33% as PD-L1-negative. To address this imbalance, the Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) was employed during pre-processing to ensure balanced model training.

2.2. Data Preprocessing

All DICOM images were imported into Python 3.8 for pre-processing and analysis. Each axial slice was resized to a standard resolution of 512×512 pixels using bilinear interpolation to normalize input dimensions and maintain consistency across all scans. Pixel intensity values were normalized to a range between 0 and 1 by dividing each pixel value by the maximum intensity in the respective slice. A Gaussian filter with a sigma value of 1 was applied using the scikit-image library to reduce noise and enhance image quality.

2.3. Lung Segmentation

Lung regions were isolated from the PET/CT scans by selecting slices numbered 120 to 260, representing the thoracic region. Otsu's thresholding method, implemented via OpenCV, was applied to each slice to generate binary masks delineating lung tissue from surrounding structures. These masks were validated by radiologists to ensure accurate segmentation.

2.4. Feature Extraction

Radiomic features were extracted using PyRadiomics, which computes a wide range of quantitative descriptors (e.g., first-order statistics, texture, and shape-based metrics). Each slice was processed individually to capture relevant heterogeneity linked to PD-L1 expression.

Two parallel datasets were created:

1. Whole-body Dataset: Radiomic features from the entire PET/CT scan.
2. Lung dataset: Radiomic features only from the lung regions (slices 120–260).

Feature-Level vs. Patient-Level Analysis

- Feature-Level: Each slice's radiomic features were treated as independent samples.
- Patient-Level: Radiomic features were aggregated by taking the mean value across all slices from each patient, resulting in a single feature vector per patient.

2.5. Feature Engineering

To enhance the model performance, feature engineering and selection were conducted in several steps. Initially, all extracted features were consolidated into a DataFrame, where non-numeric values were excluded, and missing values were replaced with zeros to ensure data completeness. Following this, feature scaling was conducted using the StandardScaler to normalize the features, making them comparable across different scales.

For the whole-body dataset at the feature level, Elastic Net regression with five-fold cross-validation using scikit-learn's ElasticNetCV was applied to identify the most predictive features, balancing L1 and L2 penalties to reduce overfitting. Features with non-zero coefficients were retained for further model development.

In contrast, for the Lung dataset and patient-level analyses, random forest feature importance was employed due to the Elastic Net's limited effectiveness in these contexts. A random forest classifier was trained, and feature importance scores were computed based on the Gini impurity criterion. Features exceeding a predefined importance threshold (importance > 0.01) were selected for model training.

2.6. Model Development, Training, and Evaluation

To predict PD-L1 expression, ensemble machine learning methods specifically random forest (RF) and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) were employed. These models were trained using radiomic features extracted from [¹⁸F]FDG PET/CT scans to classify NSCLC patients as PD-L1-positive or PD-L1-negative. Feature-level and patient-level analyses were conducted using both whole-body and Lung datasets.

2.6.1. Random Forest Models

The random forest model was developed iteratively through three phases to enhance predictive performance. Initially, a baseline model (RF Model 1) was implemented using default hyperparameters in scikit-learn as seen in Table 1 to establish a benchmark for performance evaluation. This provided a reference point for subsequent improvements. In the second phase, regularization techniques were introduced to prevent overfitting. The maximum depth of trees was constrained, and the minimum number of samples required for splitting and leaf nodes was increased. Additionally, the number of features considered per split was adjusted to ensure a balanced trade-off between model complexity and generalization.

To further refine performance, the third phase involved hyperparameter optimization, where a RandomizedSearchCV approach was applied to systematically explore and fine-tune key parameters. This process optimized the number of estimators, maximum depth, and minimum samples per split, ensuring that the model was both robust and efficient. Through this iterative approach, the random forest model was progressively improved, achieving an optimal balance between accuracy and generalizability in predicting PD-L1 expression.

2.6.2. XGBoost Models

XGBoost models were optimized in two stages. First, a baseline model (XGB Model 1) was trained using default hyperparameters to establish a benchmark. Next, hyperparameter optimization (XGB Model 2) was performed using RandomizedSearchCV to refine learning rate, maximum depth, subsample ratios, and regularization terms, improving predictive accuracy while reducing overfitting.

Model	Strategy	Parameters Tuned	Details
Random forest (RF)	Cross-validation on Base Model	Stratified 5-fold Cross-Validation	cv=5, shuffle=True, random_state=42
	Regularization (RF Model 2)	max_depth, min_samples_split, min_samples_leaf, max_features	max_depth=10, min_samples_split=5, min_samples_leaf=4, max_features='sqrt'
	Hyperparameter Tuning (RF Model 3)	Random search: n_estimators, max_depth, min_samples_split, min_samples_leaf, max_features	n_estimators=100-500, max_depth=None-50, min_samples_split=2-10, max_features=['sqrt', 'log2', None]
XGBoost	Hyperparameter Tuning (XGB Model 2)	Random search: n_estimators, learning_rate, max_depth, subsample, colsample_bytree, gamma	n_estimators=100-500, learning_rate=0.01-0.2, max_depth=3-11, subsample=0.6-1.0, gamma=0-0.3

Table 1. Summary of the hyperparameters used with the different models tested.

2.6.3. Training and Validation

The dataset was partitioned into training (80%) and testing (20%) subsets using stratified sampling to preserve class distribution. Stratified five-fold cross-validation was applied during model training to ensure robustness. Model performance was evaluated using key classification metrics, including accuracy, area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC-AUC), precision, recall, F1-score, and log loss. The results were analyzed at both feature- and patient-levels, comparing whole-body and Lung datasets to determine the most informative approach for PD-L1 prediction.

2.6.5. Software and Libraries

All analyses were performed in Python using libraries including scikit-learn for machine learning, XGBoost for gradient boosting, and PyRadiomics for feature extraction.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Lung Segmentation and Visualization

The visualization and analysis of whole-body [^{18}F]FDG PET/CT images using the Mirada DBx viewer identified slices numbered 120 to 260 as the most relevant for analysis. These slices cover the thoracic region, where NSCLC tumours are typically located. Within this slice range, the lung anatomy and tumour sites were clearly visible, as demonstrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Fused coronal PET/CT image highlighting the tumour in the right upper lung region. The lung area is indicated by the arrow, showcasing the specific region where the tumour is located.

3.2. Feature Extraction, Selection and Preprocessing

Using PyRadiomics, 98 radiomic features were initially extracted from the PET scan data for both the whole-body and lung datasets. The whole-body dataset comprised 134,590 slices,

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while the lung dataset contained 43,142 slices. For patient-level analysis, the features from all slices were aggregated using the mean, resulting in a dataset of 307 patients. These features spanned multiple categories, including statistical, texture-based, and shape-based descriptors. Feature selection methods were employed to reduce the dimensionality of the dataset. For the Whole-body dataset at feature-level, Elastic Net regression with five-fold cross-validation reduced the features to 27. In contrast, for the Lung dataset and patient-level analyses, random forest feature importance identified between 24 and 39 features, as summarized in Table 2.

Dataset	Level	Feature Selection Type	Features (Before)	Features (After)
Whole-body dataset	Feature Level	Elastic net	98	27
Whole-body dataset	Patient Level	Random forest	98	36
Lung dataset	Feature Level	Random forest	98	24
Lung dataset	Patient Level	Random forest	98	39

Table 2. Feature selection summary for whole-body and lung dataset

An initial class imbalance was observed, with PD-L1-positive cases constituting 67% of the dataset and PD-L1-negative cases 33%. SMOTE was applied to balance the dataset, resulting in an equal distribution of classes.

3.3. Model Performance (Feature-Level Analysis)

At the feature level, the random forest and XGBoost models were evaluated for both the whole-body and Lung datasets. The random forest model (RF Model 3) optimized through random search achieved the best performance on the whole-body dataset, as detailed in Table 3, with an accuracy of 99.1% and a ROC-AUC of 0.999. The cross-validation results for random forest Model 3, as shown in Table 4, reveal a consistent performance on the whole-body and Lung dataset, with mean accuracies of 0.993 and 0.758 across all five folds for the whole-body and Lung dataset respectively.

Dataset	Model	Configuration	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy	ROC-AUC
Whole-body	Random forest	Baseline RF model (RF model 1)	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.991	0.997
		Regularization (RF model 2)	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.991	0.997
		Hyperparameter tuning with random search (RF Model 3)	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.991	0.999
	XGBoost	Baseline XGB model (XGB model 1)	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.991	0.997
		Hyperparameter tuning with random search (XGB model 2)	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.991	0.998
Lung	Random forest	Baseline RF model (RF model 1)	0.72	0.71	0.72	0.71	0.76
		Regularization (RF Model 2)	0.67	0.65	0.65	0.645	0.69
		Hyperparameter tuning with random search (RF Model 3)	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.77	0.72
	XGBoost	Baseline XGB model (XGB model 1)	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.71
		Hyperparameter tuning with random search (XGB model 2)	0.72	0.72	0.72	0.72	0.75

Table 3: Performance metrics for ensemble models (feature-level analysis). The best performing model is marked in bold.

	1st Fold	2nd Fold	3rd Fold	4th Fold	5 th Fold	Mean Accuracy
Whole-body	0.994	0.993	0.993	0.993	0.993	0.993
Lung	0.760	0.763	0.745	0.756	0.765	0.758

Table 4: Cross-alidation accuracy scores for random forest in both whole-body and lung datasets (feature level analysis).

3.4. Model Performance (Patient-Level)

At the patient level, the random forest and XGBoost models were also evaluated and compared across both the whole-body and Lung datasets. The random forest model optimized through random search also exhibited the best performance, achieving the highest accuracy and ROC-AUC scores as presented in Table 5.

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Further Insight into the model's performance as depicted in Figure 2, shows high accuracy with the confusion matrix indicating correct classification of all 18 PD-L1 negative patients and 43 out of 44 PD-L1 positive patients, demonstrating near-perfect sensitivity and specificity. In **Figure 3**, the log loss analysis reveals consistently low values across most predictions, reflecting high confidence in the model's outputs. However, a distinct spike around sample index 20 suggests a single instance of high uncertainty, contrasting with the overall stability in predictive confidence throughout the dataset.

Figure 2: Confusion matrix for the random forest model optimized through random search (RF model 3) for the whole-body data at a patient level, which achieved the highest accuracy and ROC-AUC

Figure 3: Log loss result for the random forest model optimised through random search (RF model 3), for the whole-body data at a patient level, which achieved the highest accuracy and ROC-AUC.

Dataset	Model	Configuration	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy	ROC-AUC
Whole-body dataset	Random forest	Baseline RF model (RF model 1)	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.984	0.998
		Regularization (RF Model 2)	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.984	0.982
		Hyperparameter tuning with random search (RF model 3)	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.984	0.992
	XGBoost	Baseline XGB model (XGB model 1)	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.984	0.986
		Hyperparameter tuning with random search (XGB Model 2)	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.984	0.988
Lung Dataset	Random forest	Baseline RF model (RF model 1)	0.53	0.52	0.52	0.51	0.471
		Regularization (RF model 2)	0.58	0.55	0.56	0.553	0.50
		Hyperparameter tuning with random search (RF model 3)	0.58	0.56	0.57	0.565	0.511
	XGBoost	Baseline XGB model (XGB model 1)	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.613	0.558
		Hyperparameter tuning with random search (XGB model 2)	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.612	0.49

Table 5: Performance metrics for random forest (patient-level analysis)

4.0 DISCUSSION

The advent of PD-1/PD-L1 checkpoint inhibitors has transformed the treatment landscape for NSCLC, with numerous studies underscoring the importance of PD-L1 expression as a critical biomarker for predicting patient response to immunotherapy. Accurate assessment of PD-L1 levels is essential for guiding treatment decisions and optimizing outcomes in NSCLC patients [28][29][30].

In this study, radiomic features extracted from both whole-body and lung PET scan data were used to predict PD-L1 expression through feature-level and patient-level analyses. The results consistently demonstrated that whole-body data, which captures broader metabolic processes, outperformed lung data. This supports the growing evidence that incorporating whole-body imaging provides more comprehensive insights into disease processes and patient prognosis [31][32].

The evaluation of both datasets demonstrated that models trained on whole-body data consistently outperformed those trained on lung data across multiple metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and ROC-AUC scores (Tables 3 and 5). At the feature level, random forest model, chosen for its robustness against overfitting and scalability to large datasets [32], achieved a remarkable 99.1% accuracy and an ROC-AUC of 0.998 on the whole-body dataset following random search optimization (RF Model 3). In contrast, the lung data produced significantly lower results, with a maximum accuracy of 77% and ROC-AUC of 0.75 (Table 3). These results suggest that radiomic features derived from the whole body, reflecting systemic metabolic activity, offer valuable predictive information that may be absent in localized imaging focused on the lungs.

Similarly, the XGBoost models showed superior performance with whole-body data compared to lung data, reinforcing the conclusion that features from tissues beyond the lung enhance predictive accuracy. The consistent superiority of whole-body analysis indicates that broader metabolic processes are crucial for understanding PD-L1 expression in NSCLC.

Further validation using confusion matrices and log loss metrics analysis confirmed the superiority of whole-body data. The random forest and XGboost models trained on whole-body data exhibited fewer misclassifications and lower log loss values, indicating greater model confidence and reliability compared to lung-segmented models.

To ensure the model's robustness and mitigate potential overfitting, cross-validation (K-fold) was employed on the best-performing model (RF Model 3). Cross-validation, widely used to assess model performance on different subsets of data [33], confirmed the generalizability of the model. An average accuracy of 99.3% across all folds (Table 4) further validated the model's stability and reliability, indicating that it is well-suited for predicting PD-L1 expression in NSCLC.

The patient-level analysis, designed to enhance model robustness and accuracy, involved aggregating features across multiple slices using mean aggregation. This method has been shown to improve prediction performance by offering more reliable outcomes and better generalization of models [34]. In this study, patient-level analysis of the whole-body dataset

resulted in high accuracies and ROC-AUC scores, with the random forest model achieving 98% accuracy and an ROC-AUC score of 0.992, this study achieved higher ROC-AUC compared to studies [18][19] which had lower ROC-AUC scores of 68 and 84% respectively. By contrast, patient-level models trained on lung data yielded significantly lower accuracy (61.3%) and ROC-AUC (0.558), reinforcing the value of whole-body radiomics in PD-L1 prediction.

Notably, a similar study focusing on lung data achieved a ROC-AUC of 0.82 [35], further demonstrating the limitations of localized imaging approaches. In contrast, the superior performance of whole-body data in this study underscores the value of incorporating systemic metabolic information for enhanced predictive accuracy.

Overall, these findings confirm that incorporating whole-body metabolic data in radiomic analyses offers significant predictive advantages over localized imaging approaches. Previous studies reported lower accuracies when focusing only on tumour regions [18] [19], whereas this study demonstrates that whole-body analysis achieves superior predictive accuracy (99% vs. 68% and 84%, respectively). This highlights the importance of considering systemic metabolic information, rather than relying solely on localized regions, for predicting PD-L1 expression and optimizing treatment strategies in NSCLC patients.

Future studies should further investigate the potential clinical applications of whole-body radiomic analysis for broader biomarkers and treatment responses in NSCLC. The consistent results obtained in this study suggest that whole-body PET/CT data could improve patient care by providing more holistic insights into disease processes, leading to more precise treatment decisions. However, larger datasets and external validation cohorts are needed to confirm the long-term reliability and generalizability of these findings across different populations.

5.0 CONCLUSION

This study provides compelling evidence that whole-body [¹⁸F]FDG PET/CT imaging data, when analysed using machine learning models, offer a more accurate and comprehensive approach for predicting PD-L1 expression in NSCLC patients compared to lung data. The superior performance of models trained on whole-body data underscores the importance of systemic metabolic information in understanding PD-L1 expression.

By surpassing the predictive accuracy of previous studies that focused solely on localized tumor regions, this research highlights the potential clinical value of adopting a holistic imaging strategy. The incorporation of whole-body radiomic analysis could enhance patient stratification for immunotherapy, leading to improved personalized treatment strategies.

However, before this approach can be integrated into routine clinical practice, further validation in larger and more diverse patient cohorts is necessary. Future studies should also explore the integration of whole-body imaging with other data types, such as genomic and clinical information, to further enhance the predictive power of these models. Such multi-modal approaches hold promise for advancing personalized oncology care and optimizing treatment outcomes for NSCLC patients.

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